

Organic matter of clear-cut soils

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Final felling is one of the significant factors influencing changes in the structure and component composition of natural ecosystems. Soil resistance to anthropogenic impact is closely related to the qualitative and quantitative characteristics of soil organic matter (SOM). SOM is a set of organic compounds of different nature and molecular composition. A comprehensive assessment of SOM is one of the leading tasks of soil science [1]. However, the features of changes in the component composition of SOM in the process of natural restoration of woody vegetation remain poorly studied, which predetermined the purpose of this work.

The direct objects of the study were forest litters of the bilberry-green moss spruce forest (PP-1) and random uneven-aged deciduous-coniferous biocenoses formed after final felling in 2001-2002 (PP-2) and 1969-1970 (PP-3). Analytical studies were carried out according to generally accepted methods in soil science. The total content of carbon (C_{total}) and nitrogen (N_{total}) was determined by gas chromatography on a CNHS-O analyzer, the content of carbon of water-soluble organic compounds (C_{os}) was determined by high-temperature catalytic oxidation on a TOC VCPH total carbon analyzer. The mass concentration of low-molecular POC was estimated by gas chromatography and chromatograph mass spectrometry (GC/MS) [2].

In the PP-1 and PP-2 plots, the forest litters belong to the category of strongly and very strongly acidic soils, the upper horizons of the forest litter of PP-3 are characterized as slightly acidic, the lower part retains a strongly acidic reaction of the environment. The proportion of carbon C_{boc} from C_{ob} is 11-30%, the forest litters of the studied plots belong to the category of soils with an ultra-high content of WOC. In the PP-1 and PP-2 plots, the content of C_{boc} decreases with depth, in the PP-3 plot, the subhorizons of the forest litter are characterized by close values. More significant differences between the plots are observed when comparing the carbon share of the identified WOC. A similar pattern of distribution of the carbon share of the identified WOC has forest litters of the PP-1 and PP-2 plots, however, the quantitative content in the PP-2 plot is twice as small. The PP-3 plot is characterized by the maximum values, while no clear differentiation by the subhorizons of the forest litter is observed. The identified components of the WOC are dominated by carbohydrates, in particular hexoses. The process of restoration of woody vegetation is accompanied by an increase in their content. For the initial stages of restoration of woody vegetation, an increase in the proportion of alcohols in the composition of the identified WOC is noted. The content of the identified acids varies greatly depending on both the time of logging and the subhorizon of the forest litter. The mass fraction of C_{total} is within 30-48%, N_{total} - 1.4-2.1%. Despite the increase in the proportion of nitrogen in the forest litter of the soils of the clear-cut areas, the value of the C/N ratio (20 - 32) indicates their very low enrichment.

References

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